

Prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of non-ESKAPE-Ec *Enterobacteriales* in a IV-level hospital in Lima, Peru

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Summary

The aim of this work was to evaluate the levels and the evolution of antimicrobial resistance of non-ESKAPE-Ec *Enterobacteriales* (NEEeE, non *Enterococcus faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Enterobacter* spp. and *Escherichia coli*) from a IV-level Peruvian hospital. NEEeE accounting for >0.5% of total isolates in 2009-2010 (Period 1) and/or 2012-2014 (Period 2) were included in the study. Bacterial identification and antimicrobial resistance was performed by automated methods. Additionally,

the presence of extended spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBLs) was investigated in *Klebsiella oxytoca*. According to our results, *Citrobacter freundii*, *Klebsiella oxytoca*, *Morganella morganii*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Providencia* spp. and *Serratia marcescens* fulfilled inclusion criteria, accounting for 695/9918 isolates (7.0%); 238/3777 (6.30%) in Period 1 and 447/6141 (7.28%) in Period 2 ($p=0.0038$). *P. mirabilis* was the most frequent with 192 isolates (1.94%), while only 54 *Providencia* spp. (0.54%) were recovered. Carbapenems were the most active antibacterial agents. In general, the microorganisms showed lower or moderate levels of resistance to amikacin and piperacillin/tazobactam, while resistance levels to the remaining antibacterial agents were >40%. Multidrug resistance (MDR) levels varied from 36.1% in *S. marcescens* to 73.9% in *P. mirabilis*. Temporal analysis showed that the levels of antibiotic resistance tended to decrease or not to vary. This finding led to a MDR decrease, except for *P. mirabilis* and *Providencia* spp. The presence of ESBL was associated with significantly higher levels of resistance to non-cephalosporin antibiotics, except imipenem. In conclusion, present results demonstrate the relevance of NEEcE, highlighting the need to include these *Enterobacteriales* in routine follow-up and also warn about the worrisome panorama of antibiotic resistance in the area.

Key words

antimicrobial resistance *Citrobacter freundii*;
Klebsiella oxytoca; *Morganella morganii*,
Providencia; *Proteus mirabilis*; *Serratia marcescens*

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Introduction

Antibiotic resistance is an increasing problem worldwide, affecting all microorganisms irrespective of pristine or polluted environments, human or animal origin and also independently of the pathogenic characteristics.¹⁻⁶ From a human health point of view, the most relevant impact of the current levels of antimicrobial resistance is the effect on antibiotic treatments used in the course of infections or as prophylaxis when needed. Because of that, the increasing levels of antibiotic resistance, including cases of pan-drug resistance (PDR), strongly reduce the antibiotic options available, resulting in severe impacts on patient outcomes and greatly increasing final treatment costs.^{6,7}

The microorganisms collectively included under the ESKAPE-Ec acronym (*Enterococcus faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Enterobacter* spp. and *Escherichia coli*) are by far the bacteria most frequently recovered from human infections, being also a paradigm of multiresistance.^{6,8,9} Nonetheless, the impact of other microorganisms as a cause of serious human infections should also be taken into account. Several studies have described the relevance of non-ESKAPE-Ec *Enterobacteriales* as a cause of serious and deadly infectious disorders.^{5,10-12} Furthermore, the levels of antibiotic resistance exhibited by these non-ESKAPE-Ec *Enterobacteriales*, are also increasing worldwide, including MDR isolates,^{5,13,14} a growing

number of which shows resistance to last resort antibiotic treatment and, even, to newer antibiotics such as cephalosporins with β -lactamase inhibitors, carbapenems, polymyxins and/or tigecycline, among others.¹³⁻¹⁸

Most of the data about non-ESKAPE-Ec *Enterobacteriales* come from developed countries, with very fragmented or absent data from series in low- and middle-income countries. Peru is a middle-income country, in which data related to antibiotic resistance levels and mechanisms are relatively scarce and mostly focused on ESKAPE-Ec microorganisms.¹⁹⁻²³ The present report aims to analyze the isolated non-ESKAPE-Ec *Enterobacteriales* strains as a causative agent of infection in a Level IV hospital in Lima, Peru, and evaluate the evolution of antimicrobial resistance levels over time.

Material and Methods

Microorganisms

Non ESKAPE-Ec *Enterobacteriales* isolated from hospitalized patients in Internal Medicine and Surgery Departments and in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) of the *Hospital Nacional Guillermo Almenara Irigoyen* (HNGAI) were recorded in two different time periods, Period 1 from 01/01/2009 to 31/12/2010 and Period 2 from 01/01/2012 to 31/12/2014. Only species accounting for >0.5% of the total isolates in either of the study periods were included in the analysis. *Providencia* spp. was included in the analysis as a genus, because no data of specific species was available. Microorganisms from outpatients, as well as, from patients of the Emergency Department were not included in the analysis.

The samples were cultured according to conventional methods. Bacterial identification and determination of antibiotic susceptibility to cefazolin, cefotaxime, ceftriaxone, ceftazidime, cefepime, imipenem, piperacillin plus tazobactam (PTZ), cotrimoxazole, amikacin, gentamicin, tobramycin, ciprofloxacin and levofloxacin were performed by the use of the automated system MicroScan (Siemens Medical Solutions Diagnostics, Camberley, UK) in Period 1, and Microscan and VITEK 2 (bioMérieux, Marcy l'Étoile, France) in Period 2. In addition, the presence of extended-spectrum β -lactamases (ESBLs) was determined in *Klebsiella oxytoca* using the same automated methods. Antimicrobial resistance was established according to Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines.²⁴ Multidrug resistance (MDR) was defined as non-susceptibility to at least one agent of three or more antimicrobial categories.²¹

Statistical analysis

The Fisher exact test was used to determine statistical associations. A p-value <0.05 was considered as significant.

When differences in resistance levels between the two periods were greater than 5%, irrespective of the levels of significance, a trend was considered. In all cases, intermediate and susceptible-dose dependent (in the case of cefepime) isolates were classified together resistant isolates. Coagulase-negative *Staphylococcus* (CNS) were considered as contamination and not included in the statistical analyses.

Results

In the periods analyzed a total of 10,948 microorganisms were recovered from clinical samples from hospitalized patients. Of these, 1030 were CNS and were excluded from further analysis. Thus, 9918 microorganisms were considered for further analysis.

Six non-ESKAPE-EC *Enterobacteriales*: *Citrobacter freundii*, *K. oxytoca*, *Morganella morganii*, *P. mirabilis*, *Providencia* spp. and *Serratia marcescens* fulfilled the inclusion criteria, accounting for 695/9918 isolates (7.00%). Of these, 238/3777 (6.30%) were obtained in Period 1 and 447/6141 (7.28%) in Period 2. *P. mirabilis* was the most frequent of the non-ESKAPE-Ec *Enterobacteriales* with 192 isolates (1.94% of total microorganisms, 27.63% of analyzed non-ESKAPE-Ec *Enterobacteriales*), while only 54 *Providencia* spp. (0.54% of total microorganisms; 7.77% of analyzed non-ESKAPE-Ec *Enterobacteriales*) (Table 1) were recovered. When the analysis was restricted to selected non-ESKAPE-Ec *Enterobacteriales*, the results showed that in both periods *P. mirabilis* presented the higher incidence (28.15% and 27.96% in Period 1 and Period 2, respectively), while *Providencia* spp. (8.82%) and *K. oxytoca* (8.50%), showed the lower incidence values in Period 1 and Period 2, respectively (Table 2). Analysis by periods showed a bordering significant increase in the isolation of the microorganisms considered ($p=0.0665$). Thus, with the exception of *K. oxytoca*, a trend of increasing percentages was observed, with the increases of *M. morganii* and *S. marcescens* isolates being significant ($p=0.0312$ and $p<0.0001$ respectively). Meanwhile, the reductions of *K. oxytoca* were also significant ($p=0.0011$) (Table 1).

Analysis of the levels of antibiotic resistance showed carbapenems as the most active antibacterial agents against the microorganisms tested, with *Providencia* spp. and *P. mirabilis* presenting the highest levels of carbapenem resistance (in both cases < 20%). The remaining microorganisms, except for *Providencia*

Table 1 Microorganisms included in the study according to the two study periods analyzed.

Microorganisms	Period 1 (N=3777)	Period 2 (N=6141)	Overall (N=9918)
	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	67 (1.77)	125 (2.03)	192 (1.94)
<i>Citrobacter freundii</i>	55 (1.46)	93 (1.51)	148 (1.49)
<i>Morganella morganii</i>	35 (0.93) ^a	88 (1.43) ^a	123 (1.24)
<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i>	48 (1.27) ^b	38 (0.62) ^b	86 (0.87)
<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	12 (0.32) ^c	60 (0.98) ^c	72 (0.72)
<i>Providencia</i> spp.	21 (0.56)	43 (0.70)	64 (0.64)
Overall	238 (6.30)	447 (7.28)	695 (7.0)

Period 1: From January 2009 to June 2010; Period 2: From January 2012 to December 2014
^a $p = 0.0312$; ^b $p = 0.0011$; ^c $p < 0.0001$

Table 2 Incidence of selected microorganisms in the pool of analyzed non-ESKAPE-Ec *Enterobacteriales*.

Microorganisms	Period 1 (N=238)	Period 2 (N=447)	Overall (N=695)
	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	67 (28.15)	125 (27.96)	192 (27.63)
<i>Citrobacter freundii</i>	55 (23.11)	93 (20.81)	148 (21.29)
<i>Morganella morganii</i>	35 (14.71)	88 (19.69)	123 (17.70)
<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i>	48 (20.17)	38 (8.50)	86 (12.37)
<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	12 (5.11)	60 (13.42)	72 (10.36)
<i>Providencia</i> spp.	21 (8.82)	43 (9.62)	64 (9.21)

Period 1: From January 2009 to June 2010; Period 2: From January 2012 to December 2014

spp. (amikacin) and *K. oxytoca* (PTZ), showed lower or moderate levels of resistance to amikacin and PTZ. Meanwhile, as a general rule, the resistance levels to the remaining antibacterial agents were higher than 40%, reaching 92.2% in the case of *Providencia* spp. ciprofloxacin resistance levels (Table 3). Accordingly, high levels of MDR were observed, varying from 36.1% in *S. marcescens* to 73.9% in *P. mirabilis*.

The temporal analysis predominantly showed that the levels of antibiotic resistance tended to not undergo variation (differences $\leq 5\%$ between the two periods analyzed) or to decrease. This finding showed a trend towards a reduction in MDR, except in the case of *P. mirabilis*, which presented an inverse trend, and

that of *Providencia* spp. in which differences in MDR levels between the two periods were less than 5%. Interestingly, all imipenem-resistant isolates belonged to Period 2, with significant increases in the case of *P. mirabilis* ($p < 0.0001$) and *Providencia* spp. ($p = 0.0246$) (Table 3). When analyzed by microorganisms, *P. mirabilis* showed a general increase in antimicrobial resistance levels, which was also reflected in the above-mentioned non-significant increase in overall MDR levels. In the case of *S. marcescens*, although not significant, a trend to increasing levels of resistance to all β -lactam related antimicrobial agents was observed (Table 3, Table 4). In agreement with the trend to a reduction in resistance to cephalosporins, such as

Table 3 Antibiotic resistance levels.

		N	Cfz	Cxm	Ctx	Cro	Caz	Fep	Imp	PTZ	Ak	Gm	Tob	Cip	Lvx	Sxt	MDR
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	Period 1	67	64.2	65.7	50.7	50.7	50.7	49.3	0.0	7.5	26.9	56.7	55.2	73.1	62.7	68.7	67.2
	Period 2	125	81.6	ND	55.9 ^a	60.0	58.4	56.8	22.0 ^e	0.0	13.6	68.0	65.6	80.0	67.2	76.0	77.6
	<i>p</i>		0.0131	ND	---	---	---	---	<0.0001	0.0047	0.0307	---	---	---	---	---	---
	Overall	192	75.5	ND	53.2	56.8	55.7	54.2	12.7	2.6	18.2	64.1	62.0	77.6	65.6	73.4	73.9
<i>Citrobacter freundii</i>	Period 1	55	ND	69.1	61.8	56.4	60.0	49.1	0.0	36.4	23.6	63.6	52.7	70.9	70.9	74.5	74.5
	Period 2	93	ND	ND	64.8 ^b	63.4	41.9	51.6	1.1	22.1 ^g	28.0	54.8	54.8	74.2	74.2	74.2	65.6
	<i>p</i>		ND	ND	---	---	0.0405	---	---	BS	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
	Overall	148	ND	ND	63.5	60.8	48.6	50.7	0.6	28.0	26.3	58.1	54.1	73.0	73.0	74.3	68.9
<i>Morganella morganii</i>	Period 1	35	ND	ND	45.7	45.7	28.6	20.0	0.0	20.0	22.9	54.3	45.7	77.1	62.9	77.1	71.4
	Period 2	88	ND	ND	ND	43.2	22.7	36.4	10.0 ^f	3.7 ^h	17.0	35.2	43.2	67.0	50.0	63.6	54.5
	<i>p</i>		ND	ND	ND	---	---	BS	BS	0.0256	---	BS	---	---	---	---	0.0002
	Overall	123	ND	ND	ND	43.9	24.4	31.7	6.6	10.1	17.9	40.6	43.9	69.9	53.7	67.5	59.3
<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i>	Period 1	48	77.1	ND	68.8	70.8	70.8	58.3	0.0	41.7	12.5	64.6	62.5	68.8	62.5	75.0	77.1
	Period 2	38	78.9	ND	60.5	63.2	60.5	60.5	0.0	31.6	10.5	47.4	47.4	60.5	57.9	60.5	65.8
	<i>p</i>		---	ND	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
	Overall	86	77.9	ND	67.4	67.4	66.3	59.3	0.0	37.2	11.6	57.0	55.8	65.1	60.5	68.6	72.1
<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	Period 1	12	ND	ND	25.0	25.0	16.6	8.3	0.0	8.3	16.6	25.0	41.7	33.3	16.6	33.3	41.7
	Period 2	60	ND	ND	38.1 ^c	36.7	36.7	15.0	6.6	17.4 ⁱ	20.0	35.0	31.7	21.7	13.3	33.3	35.0
	<i>p</i>		ND	ND	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
	Overall	72	ND	ND	35.2	34.7	33.3	13.8	5.5	15.5	19.4	33.3	33.3	23.6	13.9	33.3	36.1
<i>Providencia</i> spp.	Period 1	21	ND	ND	85.7	85.7	33.3	76.2	0.0	76.2	57.1	95.2 ^k	85.7 ^k	90.5	85.7	61.9	71.4
	Period 2	43	ND	ND	68.0 ^d	67.5	67.5	62.8	20.9	16.0 ^j	53.5	76.7 ^k	74.4 ^k	93.2	88.4	62.8	69.8
	<i>p</i>		ND	ND	---	---	0.0153	---	0.0246	<0.0001	---	BS	---	---	---	---	
	Overall	64	ND	ND	76.1	73.4	56.2	67.2	13.1	43.5	54.7	82.8	78.1	92.2	87.3	62.5	70.3

Values expressed in percentage.

Cfz: cefazolin; Cxm: cefuroxime; Ctx: cefotaxime; Cro: ceftriaxone, Caz: ceftazidime; Fep: cefepime; Imp: imipenem; PTZ: piperacillin plus tazobactam; Ak: amikacin; Tob: tobramycin; Cip: ciprofloxacin; Lvx: levofloxacin; Sxt: cotrimoxazole; MDR: Multidrug resistance. ND: No determined. The symbol (---) refers to no significant differences. BS: Bordering significance (0.05<P<0.1).

^a Only 59 isolates tested.

^b Only 71 isolates tested.

^c Only 42 isolates tested.

^d Only 25 isolates tested.

^e Only 91 isolates tested.

^f Only 70 isolates tested.

^g Only 77 isolates tested.

^h Only 54 isolates tested.

ⁱ Only 46 isolates tested.

^j Only 25 isolates tested.

^k *Providencia stuartii* should be classified as intrinsically resistant to gentamicin and tobramycin. As no data about specific *Providencia* species was recorded, the resistance profile of these agents was not considered to establish the percentage of MDR.

Table 4 Trends of antibiotic resistance.

	Cfz	Ctx	Cro	Caz	Fep	Imp	PTZ	Ak	Gm	Tob	Cip	Lvx	Sxt	MDR
<i>P. mirabilis</i>	↑S	↑	=	↑	↑	↑S	↓S	↓S	↑	↑	↑	=	↑	↑
<i>C. freundii</i>	ND	=	↑	↓S	=	=	↓BS	=	↓	=	=	=	=	↓
<i>M. morgani</i>	ND	ND	=	↓	↑BS	↑BS	↓S	↓	↓BS	=	↓	↓	↓	↓S
<i>K. oxytoca</i>	=	↓	↓	↓	=	=	↓	=	↓	↓	↓	=	=	↓
<i>S. marcescens</i>	ND	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	=	↑	↓	↓	=	=	↓
<i>Providencia</i> spp.	ND	↓	↓	↑S	↓	↑S	↓S	=	↓BS	↓	=	=	=	=

Cfz: cefazolin; Cxm: cefuroxime; Ctx: cefotaxime; Cro: ceftriaxone, Caz: ceftazidime; Fep: cefepime; Imp: imipenem; PTZ: piperacillin plus tazobactam; Ak: amikacin; Tob: tobramycin; Cip: ciprofloxacin; Lvx: levofloxacin; Sxt: cotrimoxazole; MDR: Multidrug resistance; --- Not analyzed; S: Significant differences ($p < 0.05$); BS: Bordering significance ($0.05 < P < 0.1$).

Upper arrow: Trend to increase in resistance levels between Periods 1 and 2 (Percentual differences $> 5\%$).

Lower arrow: Trend to decrease in resistance levels between Periods 1 and 2 (Percentual differences $> 5\%$).

Equal: Percentual differences between Periods 1 and 2 $\leq 5\%$.

Marked with S and BS when significant differences were found or when bordering significance, respectively.

cefotaxime or ceftazidime, reported in *K. oxytoca*, the presence of ESBLs in this microorganism was lower in the Period 2 (66.6% vs. 57.9%). Of note, the presence of ESBL was associated with significantly higher levels of resistance to all the non-cephalosporin antibiotics studied, except imipenem (Table 5).

Discussion

While most studies address the serious problem of antibiotic resistance among ESKAPE-Ec microorganisms, other microorganisms causing severe and deadly infections are also present in hospital environments, including members of the *Enterobacteriales* family, such as *C. freundii*, *K. oxytoca* or *S. marcescens*, among others.^{10,12-14,18} These microorganisms remain understudied in most low- and middle-income countries in which data on their antibiotic resistance levels remain scarce and fragmented. In this sense, in Peru the studies analyzing the role of these microorganisms as a cause of infection or focused on (or including information of) the levels of antimicrobial resistance of the microorganisms analyzed are scarce.^{25,26} Thus, a few reports are limited to the determination of the presence of specific genes, such as carbapenemases, in hospital environments,²⁷ while others have low diffusion such as BsC theses.²⁸ The present study highlights that a relevant number of infections attended at the HNGAI (7%) are related to 6 non-ESKAPE-Ec *Enter-*

obacteriales (3 *Morganellaceae*; 2 *Enterobacteriaceae* and 1 *Yersiniaceae*), indicating that these may be truly serious overlooked and relevant under-considered pathogens in this area. Of these, significant increases in the number of *M. morgani* and *S. marcescens* were observed, and the possible introduction of successful clones should possibly be considered. In this sense, the relevance of these two microorganisms as a cause of severe infections and the presence of successful local clones has been reported.^{29,30}

In agreement with reports of resistance levels in other microorganisms isolated in Peruvian hospital settings,^{20-23,31} the present data showed high levels of resistance to most of the antimicrobials tested, with imipenem amikacin and PTZ showing overall lower levels of resistance. Low or moderate levels of amikacin and PTZ resistance has also been noted when these agents were tested in other microorganisms.^{26,31,32} Regarding imipenem, a diverse scenario is reported, with reports focused on microorganisms such as *A. baumannii* or *P. aeruginosa* showing relevant levels of resistance which are lower in other microorganisms.^{21,22,31,32}

Despite these overall high levels of antimicrobial resistance, the levels of resistance to most of the antimicrobial agents tested showed a trend to decreasing or remaining stable. This trend was reflected in lower MDR levels in 4 out of 6 microorganisms studied, with only *P. mirabilis* showing an increasing trend. The

Table 5 Association between resistance to non-cephalosporin agents and the presence of extended-spectrum β -lactamases in *Klebsiella oxytoca*.

		PTZ	Ak	Gm	Tob	Cip	Lvx	Sxt	MDR
Period 1	ESBL	77.3	27.2	84.4	84.4	84.4	81.2	87.5	100.0
	No ESBL	18.7	0.0	25.0	25.0	37.5	25.0	50.0	31.2
	<i>P</i>	0.0312	---	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0021	0.0003	0.0108	<0.0001
Period 2	ESBL	45.5	13.6	63.3	63.3	81.8	72.3	72.3	86.4
	No ESBL	12.5	6.2	25.0	25.0	31.2	31.2	37.5	18.7
	<i>P</i>	0.0403	---	0.0250	0.0250	0.0026	0.0077	0.0201	<0.0001
Overall	ESBL	50.0	16.7	75.9	75.9	83.3	79.6	83.3	94.4
	No ESBL	15.6	3.1	25.0	25.0	34.4	28.1	43.7	25.0
	<i>P</i>	<0.0001	BS	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0002	<0.0001

Fep: cefepime; Imp: imipenem; PTZ: piperacillin plus tazobactam; Ak: amikacin; Tob: tobramycin; Cip: ciprofloxacin; Lvx: levofloxacin; Sxt: cotrimoxazole; MDR: Multidrug resistance.
The symbol (---) refers to no significant differences. BS: Bordering significance (0.05<*P*<0.1).
Values expressed in percentage. No isolate was resistant to imipenem.

most notable exception was imipenem with no resistant isolate recovered in Period 1, followed by a clear increase in resistance levels in Period 2. This finding is probably related to an increasing use of carbapenemic agents. While no data of antibiotic consumption in the hospital during the periods analyzed was available, overall, antibiotic consumption in the country showed that in 2007, carbapenems ranked among the least used antibacterial agents in the country.³³ On the other hand, a report showing the use of antimicrobial agents in 3 different Peruvian hospitals showed that both imipenem and meropenem ranked among the four most used antimicrobial agents in 2016-2017.²⁵ These findings support the increasing use of these agents in Period 2, likely fueled by the lack of carbapenem resistance and the high levels of resistance to other antimicrobial agents, with the associated enhanced carbapenem pressure contributing to the selection of carbapenem-resistant microorganisms. This increase in imipenem resistance levels was absent or testimonial in only two species, *K. oxytoca* and *C. freundii*, with no specific reason explaining this difference.

While resistance levels to 3rd and 4th generation cephalosporins were high, the presence of ESBLs was only recorded for *K. oxytoca*. These ESBL-producer iso-

lates were significantly more resistant to all the antimicrobial agents tested, except amikacin ($p = 0.0831$), and accordingly, showed significantly high levels of MDR. The association between the presence of ESBL and increasing levels of resistance to other antimicrobial agents has been described previously,³⁴ also in members of the *Klebsiella* genus.¹⁹ This finding is probably related to the transferable nature of most ESBLs,³⁵ and the presence of other antimicrobial resistance determinants in the same genetic structure, which are therefore co-selected. Of note, while not significant, resistance levels to all cephalosporins tended to increase in the case of *S. marcescens*. However, it should be taken into account that this microorganism showed the lower levels of resistance to these agents in Period 1.

Regarding other antimicrobial agents, the overall high levels of resistance are in agreement with the reports of other microorganisms in the area.²⁰⁻²³ This highlights the fact that the use of these antimicrobial agents is heavily challenged, and they should be used with special caution, avoiding, whenever possible, their empiric uses in the absence of established antimicrobial susceptibility profiles. In concordance, the levels of MDR were high, with *S. marcescens* being the microorganisms with the lowest MDR values in both

of the periods analyzed and as overall data.

This study has several limitations, the most relevant being the lack of data regarding clinical outcomes, which is key to better analyzing the relevance of antimicrobial-resistant phenotypes. Nevertheless, the high levels of antibiotic resistance observed clearly demonstrate the need to introduce corrective and control measures. In this sense, in 2018, after Period 2, HNGAI established a Program for Optimization of Antibiotic use (PROA) to fight this problem.

The present data highlight the need to include microorganisms beyond classical members of the ES-KAPE-Ec group in routine follow-up, and also warn about the worrisome panorama of antibiotic resistance in the country.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.

Περίληψη

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Σκοπός της παρούσας εργασίας ήταν να αξιολογήσει τα επίπεδα και την εξέλιξη της μικροβιακής αντοχής των μη ESKAPE-Ec *Enterobacteriales* (NEEce, όχι *Enterococcus faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Enterobacter* spp. και *Escherichia coli*) σε τριτοβάθμιο νοσοκομείο στο Περού. Στη μελέτη συμπεριλήφθηκαν τα NEEce που απομονώθηκαν τα διαστήματα 2009-2010 (Περίοδος 1) και 2012-2014 (Περίοδος 2) και αντιπροσώπευαν >0,5% των συνολικών απομονώσεων. Η βακτηριακή ταυτοποίηση και η μικροβιακή αντοχή έγινε με αυτοματοποιημένες μεθόδους. Επιπρόσθετα, διερευνήθηκε η παρουσία β-λακταμασών εκτεταμένου φάσματος (ESBLs) στα στελέχη *Klebsiella oxytoca*. Σύμφωνα με τα αποτελέσματά της μελέτης, *Citrobacter freundii*, *K. oxytoca*, *Morganella morganii*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Providencia* spp. και *Serratia marcescens* πληρούσαν τα κριτήρια ένταξης, αντιπροσωπεύοντας 695/9918 απομονώσεις (7,0%) [238/3777 (6,30%) την Περίοδο 1 και 447/6141 (7,28%) την Περίοδο 2 (p=0,0038)]. Το είδος *P. mirabilis* ήταν το πιο συχνό με 192 απομονώσεις (1,94%), ενώ απομονώθηκαν μόνο 54 στελέχη *Providencia* spp. (0,54%). Οι καρβαπενέμες ήταν οι πιο δραστικοί αντιμικροβιακοί παράγοντες. Γενικά, οι μικροοργανισμοί παρουσίασαν χαμηλότερα ή μέτρια επίπεδα αντοχής στην αμικασίνη και την πιπερακιλλίνη/ταζομπακτάμη, ενώ τα επίπεδα αντοχής στα υπόλοιπα αντιμικροβιακά ήταν >40%. Τα πολυανθεκτικά στελέχη (MDR) κυμαίνονταν από 36,1% στα στελέχη *S. marcescens* έως 73,9% στα στελέχη *P. mirabilis*. Η σύγκριση των χρονικών περιόδων έδειξε ότι τα επίπεδα αντοχής στα αντιβιοτικά έτειναν να μειώνονται ή να παραμένουν σταθερά. Παρατηρήθηκε μείωση απομόνωσης των MDR, εκτός από τα στελέχη *P. mirabilis* και *Providencia* spp. Η παρουσία ESBL συσχετίστηκε με σημαντικά υψηλότερα επίπεδα αντοχής στα λοιπά, πλην των κεφαλοσπορινών, αντιβιοτικά, εκτός από την ιμιπενέμη. Συμπερασματικά, τα παρόντα αποτελέσματα καταδεικνύουν τη σημασία των NEEce, υπογραμμίζοντας την ανάγκη να συμπεριληφθούν αυτά τα Εντεροβακτηριακά στην παρακολούθηση ρουτίνας της αντοχής στα αντιμικροβιακά και επίσης προειδοποιούν σε τοπικό επίπεδο για το ανησυχητικό φαινόμενο της πολυαντοχής.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

αντιμικροβιακή αντοχή, *Citrobacter freundii*, *Klebsiella oxytoca*, *Morganella morganii*, *Providencia*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Serratia marcescens*

References

- Bartoloni A, Pallecchi L, Benedetti M, Fernandez C, Vallejos Y, Guzman E, *et al.* Multidrug-resistant commensal *Escherichia coli* in children, Peru and Bolivia. *Emerg Infect Dis.* 2006; 12:907-913.
- Chen H, Bai X, Jing L, Chen R, Teng Y. Characterization of antibiotic resistance genes in the sediments of an urban river revealed by comparative metagenomics analysis. *Sci Total Environ.* 2019; 653:1513-1521. doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.11.052.
- Hernández J, González-Acuña D. Anthropogenic antibiotic resistance genes mobilization to the polar regions. *Infect Ecol Epidemiol.* 2016; 6:32112. doi: 10.3402/iee.v6.32112.
- Loyola S, Gutierrez L, Avendaño E, Severino N, Tamariz J. Multidrug-resistant bacteria isolated from cell phones in five intensive care units: Exploratory dispersion analysis. *Germes.* 2018; 8:85-91. doi: 10.18683/germes.2018.1135.
- Mandomando I, Bassat Q, Sigaúque B, Massora S, Quintó L, Ácacio S, *et al.* Invasive *Salmonella* infections among children from rural Mozambique, 2001-2014. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2015;61 Suppl 4: S339-345. doi: 10.1093/cid/civ712.
- Pons MJ, Ruiz J. Current trends in epidemiology and antimicrobial resistance in Intensive Care Units. *J Emerg Crit Care Med* 2019; 3:5.
- Elemam A, Rahimian J, Mandell W. Infection with panresistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae*: a report of 2 cases and a brief review of the literature. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2009; 49:271-274. doi: 10.1086/600042.
- De Angelis G, Fiori B, Menchinelli G, D'Inzeo T, Liotti FM, Morandotti GA, *et al.* Incidence and antimicrobial resistance trends in bloodstream infections caused by ESKAPE and *Escherichia coli* at a large teaching hospital in Rome, a 9-year analysis (2007-2015). *Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis.* 2018; 37:1627-1636. doi: 10.1007/s10096-018-3292-9.
- Santajit S, Indrawattana N. Mechanisms of antimicrobial resistance in ESKAPE pathogens. *Biomed Res Int.* 2016; 2016:2475067. doi: 10.1155/2016/2475067.
- Åttman E, Korhonen P, Tammela O, Vuento R, Aittoniemi J, Syrjänen J, *et al.* A *Serratia marcescens* outbreak in a neonatal intensive care unit was successfully managed by rapid hospital hygiene interventions and screening. *Acta Paediatr.* 2018;107:425-429. doi: 10.1111/apa.14132.
- Cardoso NA, Cisneros LL, Machado CJ, Procópio RJ, Navarro TP. Risk factors for mortality among patients undergoing major amputations due to infected diabetic feet. *J Vasc Bras.* 2018; 17:296-302. doi: 10.1590/1677-5449.010717.
- Lee R, Choi SM, Jo SJ, Lee J, Cho SY, Kim SH, *et al.* Clinical characteristics and antimicrobial susceptibility trends in *Citrobacter* bacteremia: an 11-year single-center experience. *Infect Chemother.* 2019; 51:1-9. doi: 10.3947/ic.2019.51.1.1.
- Ghaith DM, Zafer MM, Ismail DK, Al-Agamy MH, Bohol MFF, Al-Qahtani A, *et al.* First reported nosocomial outbreak of *Serratia marcescens* harboring *bla*_{IMP-4} and *bla*_{VIM-2} in a neonatal intensive care unit in Cairo, Egypt. *Infect Drug Resist.* 2018;11:2211-2217. doi: 10.2147/IDR.S174869
- Pérez-Vázquez M, Oteo-Iglesias J, Sola-Campoy PJ, Carrizo-Manzoni H, Bautista V, Lara N, *et al.* Characterization of carbapenemase-producing *Klebsiella oxytoca* in Spain, 2016-2017. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother.* 2019; 63: e02529-18. doi: 10.1128/AAC.02529-18.
- Granda A, Riveros M, Martínez-Puchol S, Ocampo K, Laureano-Adame L, Corujo A, *et al.* Presence of extended-spectrum β -lactamase, CTX-M-65, in *Salmonella enterica* serovar Infantis isolated from children with diarrhea in Lima, Peru. *J Pediatric Infect Dis* 2019; 14:194-200.
- He T, Wang R, Liu D, Walsh TR, Zhang R, Lv Y, *et al.* Emergence of plasmid-mediated high-level tigecycline resistance genes in animals and humans. *Nat Microbiol.* 2019;4:1450-1456. doi: 10.1038/s41564-019-0445-2.
- Luk-In S, Chatsuwat T, Pulsrikarn C, Bangtrakulnonth A, Rirerm U, Kulwichit W. High prevalence of ceftriaxone resistance among invasive *Salmonella enterica* serotype Choleraesuis isolates in Thailand: The emergence and increase of CTX-M-55 in ciprofloxacin-resistant *S. Choleraesuis* isolates. *Int J Med Microbiol.* 2018; 308: 447-553. doi: 10.1016/j.ijmm.2018.03.008.
- Simon M, Melzl H, Hiergeist A, Richert K, Falgenhauer L, Pfeifer Y, *et al.* Colistin- and carbapenem-resistant *Klebsiella oxytoca* harboring *bla*_{VIM-2} and an insertion in the *mgrB* gene isolated from blood culture. *Int J Med Microbiol.* 2017; 307:113-115. doi: 10.1016/j.ijmm.2017.01.001.
- García C, Astocondor L, Rojo-Bezarez B, Jacobs J, Sáenz Y. Molecular characterization of extended-spectrum β -Lactamase-producer *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates causing neonatal sepsis in Peru. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 2016; 94:285-288. doi: 10.4269/ajtmh.15-0373.
- García C, Horna G, Linares E, Ramírez R, Tapia E, Velásquez J, *et al.* Antimicrobial drug resistance in Peru. *Emerg Infect Dis.* 2012; 18:520-521. doi: 10.3201/eid1803.100878.
- Horna G, Quezada K, Ramos S, Mosqueda N, Rubio

- M, Guerra H, *et al.* Specific type IV pili groups in clinical isolates of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *Int Microbiol.* 2019; 22:131-141. doi: 10.1007/s10123-018-00035-3.
22. Levy-Blitchein S, Roca I, Plasencia-Rebata S, Vicente-Taboada W, Velásquez-Pomar J, Muñoz L, *et al.* Emergence and spread of carbapenem-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* international clones II and III in Lima, Peru. *Emerg Microbes Infect.* 2018;7:119. doi: 10.1038/s41426-018-0127-9
 23. Palma N, Pons MJ, Gomes C, Mateu J, Riveros M, García W, *et al.* Resistance to quinolones, cephalosporins and macrolides in *Escherichia coli* causing bacteraemia in Peruvian children. *J Glob Antimicrob Resist.* 2017; 11:28-33.
 24. Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute. Performance standards for antimicrobial susceptibility testing. Document M100 - S24. Wayne, CLSI, 2014.
 25. Hernández-Gómez C, Hercilla L, Mendo F, Pérez-Lazo G, Contreras E, Ramírez E, *et al.* Programas de optimización del uso de antimicrobianos en Perú: Un acuerdo sobre lo fundamental. *Rev Chil Infectol* 2019; 36: 565-575. doi: 10.4067/S0716-10182019000500565.
 26. Miranda J, Pinto J, Faustino M, Sánchez-Jacinto B, Ramírez F. Resistencia antimicrobiana de uropatógenos en adultos mayores de una clínica privada de Lima, Perú. *Rev Peru Med Exp Salud Publica* 2019; 36: 87-92. doi:10.17843/rpmesp.2019.361.3765.
 27. Sacaquispe-Contreras R, Bailón-Calderón H. Identificación de genes de resistencia a carbapenémicos en enterobacterias de hospitales de Perú, 2013-2017. *Rev Peru Med Exp Salud Publica.* 2018;35:259-264. doi: 10.17843/rpmesp.25Y.25v25i.3474.
 28. Torres Mendoza LK. Perfil microbiológico y resistencia bacteriana de infecciones del tracto urinario en pacientes hospitalizados del servicio de medicina del hospital nacional Edgardo Rebagliati Martins en el año 2015. Lima - Perú. [BsC Thesis]. Huancayo (Peru), Universidad Nacional del Centro de Peru, 2015
 29. Liu H, Zhu J, Hu Q, Rao X. *Morganella morganii*, a non-negligent opportunistic pathogen. *Int J Infect Dis.* 2016;50:10-17. doi: 10.1016/j.ijid.2016.07.006.
 30. Vetter L, Schuepfer G, Kuster SP, Rossi M. A hospital-wide outbreak of *Serratia marcescens*, and Ishikawa's "fishbone" analysis to support outbreak control. *Qual Manag Health Care.* 2016;25:1-7. doi: 10.1097/QMH.0000000000000078.
 31. Naomi-Matsuoka A, Vargas M, Ymaña B, Soza G, Pons MJ. Resistencia a la colistina en cepas de *Klebsiella pneumoniae* multidrogoresistente del período 2015 2018 en un instituto materno perinatal de Lima, Perú. *Rev Peru Med Exp Salud Publica* 2020; 37:716-720. doi: 10.17843/rpmesp.2020.374.5422.
 32. Quispe AM, Soza G, Pons MJ. Multidrug resistance and its association with *Enterobacteriales* and age among pregnant Peruvian women with bacteremia. *J Infect Dev Ctries* 2020; 14:1402-1409. doi: 10.3855/jidc.12569.
 33. Wirtz VJ, Dreser A, Gonzales R. Trends in antibiotic utilization in eight Latin American countries, 1997-2007. *Rev Panam Salud Publica.* 2010;27:219-225. doi: 10.1590/s1020-49892010000300009.
 34. Alqasim A, Abu Jaffal A, Alyousef AA. Prevalence of multidrug resistance and extended-Spectrum β -lactamase carriage of clinical uropathogenic *Escherichia coli* isolates in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *Int J Microbiol.* 2018;2018:3026851. doi: 10.1155/2018/3026851.
 35. Bush K, Bradford PA. Epidemiology of β -lactamase-producing pathogens. *Clin Microbiol Rev.* 2020;33:e00047-19. doi: 10.1128/CMR.00047-19.